

**EFFICACY OF VIRECHANA KARMA ALONG WITH SHAMANA
YOGA IN SHEETAPITTA W.S.R. URTICARIA: A SINGLE CASE STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Sheetapitta* is described in the *Ayurvedic* classics as one of the *Twak vikara*. It is considered a *Tridoshaja vyadhi*, often triggered by factors such as exposure to cold, indigestion, incompatible diet, and psychological disturbances. Predominately, it involves the vitiation of *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha* in association with *Pitta Dosha*. The condition manifests with *Varti Damshavat Shotha* and *Kandu* due to aggravated *Kapha*, *Shula* due to *Vata*, and *Daha* because of *Pitta*. Clinically, *Sheetapitta* is correlated with urticaria, a vascular reaction characterized by transient, erythematous, edematous wheals or papules of varying shapes and sizes, typically associated with pruritus. **Aim and Objectives:** The study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of *Ayurvedic* mangement – both *Shodhana Chikitsa* and *Shamana Chikitsa* in the management of *Sheetapitta*. **Material and Methods:** A single case study was conducted on a 28- year old male patient presenting with reddish, irregular, elevated skin lesions accompanied by itching and

burning sensation for the past 8 months. The symptoms were aggravated by the intake of hot, sour spicy, oily fermented food items, citrus fruits, dry fruits, and exposure to cold air or dust. The condition worsened at night and subsided by morning. Based on clinical features, the

diagnosis of *Sheetapitta* was established. **Results:** Implementation of *Ayurvedic* management through *Shodhana* and *Shamana Chikitsa* showed significant improvement in symptoms, effectively controlling *Sheetapitta* (urticaria) and enhancing the patients quality of life. **Conclusion:** The case report demonstrates that classical *Ayurvedic* treatment protocols for *Sheetapitta* can provide considerable relief and are effective in managing urticaria.

KEYWORDS: *Sheetapitta*, Urticaria, *Shodhana Chikitsa*, *Shamana Chikitsa*, *Ayurveda*.

INTRODUCTION

In *Ayurveda*, *Sheetapitta* is described as one of the *Twak Vikara*. The term is composed of two words – *Sheeta* and *Pitta* – which are opposite in meaning. *Sheeta* denotes the influence of *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha*, while *Pitta* represents its association with *Pitta Dosha*. According to *Madhava Nidana*, *Sheetapitta* manifests with the sudden appearance of symptoms such as intense itching, burning and excessive secretions, commonly triggered by exposure to cold or hot air. This condition predominantly involves the vitiation of *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha*, along with *Pitta Dosha*.^[1]

The deranged *Doshas* subsequently cause *Rasa* and *Rakta Dhatu Dushti*, which extend to the extremities resulting in maculopapular eruptions. Classical *Ayurvedic* texts mention three closely related conditions – *Sheetapitta*, *Udarda*, and *Kotha* – each with distinct causative factors and clinical features. Although specific references to *Sheetapitta* are not directly found in the *Brihatrayi*, these terms are described under *Purvarupa*^[2], *Lakshana*^[3] and *Vyadhi*.^[4] *Madhukosa* further clarifies that while the clinical features of *Sheetapitta* and *Udarda* are similar, *Sheetapitta* is dominated by *Vata Dosha*, whereas *Udarda* has a *Kapha* predominance.^[5] The etiological factors of *Sheetapitta* include the intake of *Asatmya Ahara* (incompatible foods) and exposure to various allergens. In the context of modern lifestyles, irregular dietary habits and poor nutritional intake lead to *Dhatu Daurbalya* and impaired immune function. This lowers the body's resistance, resulting in hypersensitivity to allergens and allergic manifestations. Based on the similarity in causative factors and clinical presentation, *Sheetapitta* can be correlated with urticaria. Urticaria is common dermatological condition that affects nearly 20% of the population at some point in their lifetime.^[6] Although not life – threatening it significantly impairs the quality of life due to its distressing symptoms. The term “urticaria” is derived from the latin word *urtica*, meaning stinging nettle, which reflects the typically stinging and itching sensations associated with the disease. Clinically, urticaria is characterised by erythematous, pruritic wheals involving the dermis

and mucous membranes, caused by capillary dilation and increased vascular permeability.^[7] its etiology is multifactorial, including IgE mediated food and drugs reactions, physical stimuli, infections, and autoimmune conditions.^[8] Urticaria may present as acute or chronic. Acute urticaria is usually widespread, lasts less than six weeks, and is often linked to type I hypersensitivity reactions.^[9] chronic urticaria persists beyond six weeks and in up to 45% of cases, an autoimmune mechanism is implicated.^[10]

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To study about *Sheetapitta Vyadhi* (Urticaria) and to assess the competency of *Shodhana chikitsa & Shamana chikitsa* in *Sheetapitta Vyadhi*.

CASE REPORT

A 28 year old male patient with medium built reported to OPD and presented complaints of elevated reddish irregular lesions with swelling. The above complaints associated with gradual onset of itching and burning sensation all over the body since 8 months. Itching starts immediately after the consumption of food items like hot sour, spices, citrus fruits, oily food, dry fruits and contact with cold air and dust. The symptoms aggravated more in the night and gradually subside in the morning. The diagnosis was done as *Sheetapitta* on the basis of etiological factors and clinical presentation.

History of present illness

The patient was in good health until 8 months back, when he noticed the gradual appearance of reddish, irregular patches all over the body. He initially ignored the symptoms, but as they became severe, he visited an allopathic hospital and took treatment for 8 months. Though she felt better while on medication, the lesions came back after stopping the treatment. Therefore, he decided to try *Ayurvedic* treatment.

Past history

Patient had no history of any systemic disease, no medical or surgical history.

Personal history

Occupation – student.

Nidana^[11]

Due to *Sheeta Marutadi Sevan* (exposure to cold wind and cold weather), *Kapha* and *Vata Dosh*a gets vitiated and mixed with *Pitta Dosh*a. All the three vitiated *Dosh*as spreads all over

the body and manifests as *Sheetapitta*.

1. *Aharaj Hetu* – *Atiamla Sevan, Atilavan, Atikatu Sevan, Kshara Sevan, Viruddha Ahar Sevan, Dadhi Sevan.*

2. *Viharaj Hetu* – *Sheet Maruta Sevan, Bahaya Krumi, Keeta Damsga, Chardi Nigrahan, Shishir Ritu, Vastra, Abhushan.*

Nidanaarthakara Roga – *Pittaja and Kaphaja Jwara, Sannipatika Roga, Unmarda, Adhoga Amlapitta.*

***Poorvarupa*^[12]**

Pipasa (thirst), *Aruchi* (loss of appetite), *Hrillasa* (nausea), *Dehasaad* (feeling of tiredness), *Anga Gaurava* (feeling of heaviness), *Rakta Lochanata* (Redness of eye).

***Rupa*^[13]**

Varti Damshta Samsthana Shotha (inflammation like an insect bite), *Kandu Bahula* (severe itching), *Toda Bahula* (excessive pain like pricking), *Chardi* (vomiting), *Jvara* (fever), *Vidaha* (burning sensation), *Kasnikotpatti Vinasha*.

Samprapti Ghataka

- *Dosha - Tridosha*
- *Agni - Mandagni*
- *Vyadhimarga - Bahya*
- *Dushya - Rasa, Rakta*
- *Srotas - Rasavaha, Raktavaha*
- *Srotodushtiprakara - Vimarga Gamana*
- *Udbhavasthana - Aamashaya*
- *Vyaktisthana - Tvak*
- *Svabhava - Ashukari*

General Examination

- Pulse - 80/min
- B.P - 120/80 mmhg
- RR - 18/min
- Temp - 98.2°F
- Weight - 70kg
- Height - 5.5''

- Appetite - normal
- Sleep - sound

Table No. 1: Ashtavidha pariksha of patient.

Name	Lakshana
Nadi (Pulse)	<i>Kapha Pitta Predominant</i>
Mala (stool)	<i>Niram</i>
Mutra (Urine)	<i>Samanya</i>
Jivha (Tongue)	<i>Saam</i>
Shabda (Speech)	<i>Spashta</i>
Sparsa (Touch)	<i>Anushnasheeta</i>
Druk (Eye)	<i>Samyak</i>
Aakruti (Appearance)	<i>Madhyam</i>

Assessment Criteria

The patient assessment was carried out based on the improvement in subjective parameters, such as *Kotha* (inflammation), *Kandu* (itching) and *Daha* (burning sensation) *Toda* (pricking sensation)

Table No. 2: Subjective criteria.

Symptoms	Mild	Moderate	Severe
<i>Kotha</i> (raised oedematous wheels of pink red colour)	1	2	3
<i>Kandu</i> (itching)	1	2	3
<i>Daha</i> (burning sensation)	1	2	3
<i>Toda</i> (pricking sensation)	1	2	3

Treatment

Shodhan Chikitsa – Virechana Karma Shamana Chikitsa – Haridrakhanda^[14]

Medicine for *Virechana Karma- Trivrit Avaleha*^[15] *Virechanopag Dravya - Draksha Kashaya*^[16]

Local application – Coconut oil mix with Camphor.

Table no. 3: Medicine and Dose Schedule.

S.NO.	Procedure	Medicine	Dose	Duration
1	<i>Deepana & Pachana</i>	<i>Chitrakadi Vati</i> ^[17]	2 BD after meal	5 days
2	<i>Snehapana</i>	<i>Panchatikta Ghrita</i> ^[18]	As per <i>Kostha</i> and agni	5 days
3	<i>Sarvanga Abhyanga</i>	<i>Kayakalp Taila</i>	30 minutes	3 days
4	<i>Sarvanga Vashpa Swedana</i>	<i>Dashmoola Kwath</i>	10 – 15 min	3 days

5	<i>Virechana</i>	<i>Trivrit Avaleha</i>	60 gm	1 day
		<i>Draksha Kashaya</i>	150 ml	
6	<i>Sansarjaan Karma</i>	-	<i>Madhayam Suddhi</i>	5 days
7	<i>Shamana chikitsa</i>	<i>Haridrakhanda</i>	2 tsf BD with milk	1 month
		Coconut oil mix with camphor	Local application	

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Following the initiation of treatment, noticeable improvement in the patient sign and symptoms was observed within 15 days. By the second follow up visit, significant relief was noted in *Kotha* (inflammation), *Kandu* (itching), *Daha* (burning sensation), and *Toda* (pricking sensation).

Before treatment

After treatment

Table no. 4: OBSERVATION.

S.NO	Symptoms	Obseved score	
		Before treatment	After treatment
1	<i>Kotha</i> (raised oedamatous wheels of pink red colour)	3	1
	<i>Kandu</i> (itching)	3	1
	<i>Daha</i> (burning sensation)	3	0
	<i>Toda</i> (pricking sensation)	2	0

Table no. 5: PATHYA – APTHYA.^[19]

<i>Pathya Ahara</i>	<i>Apathya Ahara</i>
<i>Jererna Shali</i>	<i>Ksheera Vikarani</i>
<i>Jangala Mamsa</i>	<i>Chhardi Nigraha</i>
<i>Triphala</i>	<i>Ikshu Vikarani</i>
<i>Madhu</i>	<i>Divaswapna</i>
<i>Mudga Yusha</i>	<i>Matsya</i>
<i>Kulattha Yusha</i>	<i>Poorva and Daksheena Disha Pavana</i>
<i>Ushnodaka</i>	<i>Anupa Audak Mamsa</i>
<i>Karkotaka Shaka</i>	<i>Snana</i>
<i>Karavellaka Shaka</i>	<i>Naveena Madhya</i>
<i>Moolak Yusha</i>	<i>Atapa Sevana</i>
<i>Dadima Phala</i>	<i>Virudhahara</i>
<i>Shigru Shaka</i>	<i>Vyavaya</i>
<i>Moolaka Shaka</i>	<i>Snigdha, Amla, Madhura Dravya</i>
<i>Vetragra Phala</i>	<i>Guru Annapana</i>
<i>Potika Phala</i>	
<i>Katu Rasa, Tikta Rasa, Kasaya Rasa</i>	

DISCUSSION

According to *Ayurveda*, *Sheetapitta* is a *Tridoshaja Vyadhi* (disorder involving all three doshas), characterised by symptoms such as *Kotha* (inflammation), *Kandu* (itching), *Daha* (Burning sensation), *Toda* (pricking sensation). In modern science, *Sheetapitta* is correlated with *Urticaria*. Skin disorders not only cause physical discomfort but also lead to cosmetic disfigurement, thereby affecting the patient psychological and social well-being.

Ayurveda recommends a comprehensive line of treatment where aggravated *Doshas* are first eliminated through *Panchakarma* therapy, followed by *Shamana* therapy to pacify the remaining vitiated *Doshas*, as described in classical texts. In *Sheetapitta*, *Vata* and *Kapha* are primarily vitiated along with *Pitta*. The aggravated *Kapha* combines with *Pitta* and due to *Vata* involvement, the *Doshas* spread throughout the *Twak* (skin), causing widespread lesions (*Vimargagamana*) *Virechana Karma* is considered a specific treatment for *Pitta* doshas as per *Charaka*, and it is also indicated in *Pitta-Samsargaja* and *Kapha Samsargaja* disorders, as well as *Pitta Sthanagata Kapha*, according to *Vagabhata*. In this case, predominant involvement of *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Rakta* was noted, with relatively less involvement of *Kapha*. Since the lesions were mainly localized to the upper and lower limbs, *Virechana* was planned as a purification measure using *Trivrit Avaleha* and *Draksha Kashaya*. Initially, when the patient consulted the OPD, the condition was severe; therefore, *Chitrakadi Vati (Deepana – Pachana)* were administered for 5 days internally to improve *Agni* and correct *Ama*. Thereafter, *Snehapana* with *Panchtikta ghrita* was done for 5 days to pacify *Vata Pitta Dosh* and prepare

the body for *Virechana Karma*. *Abhyanga* with *Kayakalp Taila* and *Swedana* with *Dashmoola Kwath* were carried out for 3 days to liquefy the vitiated *Doshas* and bring them towards the *Koshta* for elimination.

Virechana Karma was performed using *Trivrit Avaleha* and *Draksha Kashaya* which result in *Madhyama Shuddhi*. *Virechana* is the prime therapy for elimination of *Pitta* and associated *Doshas*. After *Virechana*, resulting in significant reduction of lesions over the extremities and overall symptomatic relief. Subsequently, *Shamana Chikitsa* was planned with *Haridrakhanda* (2 tsf BD). Its main ingredients, *Haridra* (*Curcuma longa*) possesses potent anti – allergic properties and is widely recommended for allergic conditions like urticaria (*Sheetapitta*) and other skin disease. Coconut oil mixed with camphor was advised for external use twice daily for one month. Coconut oil provides cooling, soothing, and moisturizing effects, while camphor reduces itching (*Kandu*) and inflammation (*Kotha*), giving a mild cooling sensation. This combination helped relieve *Kandu* (itching) *Daha* (burning) and improved skin healing.

CONCLUSION

The integrated *Ayurvedic* approach comprising *Virechana Karma* followed by *Shamana Chikitsa* provided marked improvement in the cardinal symptoms of *Sheetapitta* (urticaria) – namely *Kotha*, *Kandu*, *Daha*, *Toda* – with no recurrence during follow up. This case highlights that the classical line of treatment of *Ayurveda* is a safe and effective modality, addressing both symptoms relief and the root cause, thereby improving the overall quality of life.

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